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SurpriseLSTM: Neural Modeling of Musical Expectation and Surprise in Monophonic Melodies

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Abstract

We introduce *SurpriseLSTM*, an LSTM network that predicts note-by-note surprisal in strictly monophonic, symbolic melodies. We conduct the first systematic comparisons of a neural expectancy model against the symbolic IDyOM model and the audio-based AudioIC algorithm across five complementary validation paradigms: large-scale correlations on Western melody corpora, two-note pleasantness ratings, Bach-chorale surprise profiles, and the musical Wundt effect. *SurpriseLSTM* matches or exceeds the performance of IDyOM in aligning with human surprise judgments. A detailed context analysis reveals distinct differences in how neural and statistical models respond to authentic cadences versus non-cadential situations, with *SurpriseLSTM* showing superior containment rates and distribution fitting in predicting human scale degree expectations. These findings demonstrate that recurrent neural networks, trained on basic note-level features, can accurately capture the cognitive principles of statistical learning and probabilistic prediction in music perception. Code and a pre-trained model are available at <https://github.com/lissenko/surprise-lstm>.

Keywords: Musical surprise; Information content; LSTM; IDyOM

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Music has the ability to create expectations in listeners and then eventually surprise by violating those expectations. When we hear the opening notes of a familiar melody, we unconsciously anticipate what comes next. Sometimes our predictions are confirmed, creating a sense of satisfaction. Other times, the music takes an unexpected turn. We might encounter a surprising chord change, an unusual melodic leap, or an unexpected rhythm, creating moments of tension, excitement, or delight.

Take Beethoven's Fifth Symphony: the opening *da-da-da-DUM* motif creates a clear pattern that listeners learn quickly. When this pattern returns later, sometimes unchanged and sometimes varied, it confirms or surprises our expectations. In jazz standards like *Autumn Leaves*, musicians first play the melody as written, setting up what listeners expect to hear. Then they improvise variations that change the melody while keeping the basic chord structure.

This interplay between expectation and surprise plays important part of our musical aesthetic experience [1]. It contributes to our emotional response, and our engagement with the music. Moreover if a piece is entirely predictable, it may feel boring and if the piece is completely unpredictable, it may feel chaotic and unpleasant. The music we like often has a balance between expectations violation and confirmation.

Understanding how these expectations form and how surprise affects our musical experience is therefore crucial for several reasons. First, it reveals fundamental aspects of human cognition: how we learn patterns, make predictions, and adapt to new information in real time. Second, it helps explain why certain musical structures are found across cultures and historical periods, suggesting the psychological principles that govern musical aesthetics. Third, as artificial intelligence systems increasingly generate music, the ability to model and control musical surprise becomes essential for creating compositions that feel both coherent and engaging to human listeners.

1.2 Background and context

The scientific study of musical expectation has evolved through several phases. In the 1950s, music theorist Leonard Meyer proposed that musical meaning emerges from the creation and resolution of expectations: when music confirms what we anticipate, we feel satisfaction; when it violates our predictions, we experience tension or surprise [2]. Building on this foundation, researchers developed rule-based theories to explain how these expectations form, drawing on principles from music theory and perceptual psychology [3, 4, 5, 1]. Since the 1990s, however, a different approach has emerged based on implicit statistical learning. This theory proposes that listeners unconsciously absorb the statistical regularities of musical styles through mere exposure, gradually building internal models that allow them to predict likely melodic and harmonic continuations [6, 7, 8]. This learning process operates automatically, without conscious effort or formal musical training, and follows similar principles observed in language acquisition and other cognitive domains [9, 10, 11].

1.3 Problem statement

Recent decades have seen the development of computational models that attempt to capture these processes. The most prominent is IDyOM (Information Dynamics of Music), which uses statistical techniques to predict the next note in a melody and quantifies surprise as the *information content* of unexpected events. Such models have successfully predicted aspects of human musical perception and have found

applications in music analysis, composition, and even neuroscience research [7, 8, 12, 13, 14, 15].

However, computational modeling has evolved with the rise of deep learning. Neural networks have demonstrated important abilities to learn complex patterns in sequential data, from natural language [16, 17, 18] to music [19, 20]. This raises fundamental questions: Can modern neural architectures capture the same principles of musical expectation that govern human cognition? How do their predictions compare to established statistical models? And perhaps most importantly, do they align with human judgments of musical surprise?

This thesis addresses these questions by focusing on the case of monophonic melodies: single lines of music without harmonic accompaniment. While simpler than full musical textures, monophonic melodies contain the essential ingredients of musical expectation: patterns of pitch and rhythm that create predictable structures and opportunities for surprise.

1.4 Research objectives

To address these gaps, we pursue three interrelated goals:

1. **Neural instantiation of SLH and PPH:** Develop SurpriseLSTM, a recurrent network that instantiate the statistical learning and probabilistic prediction hypothesis and learns transition statistics and outputs pitch-prediction distributions suitable for information-content computation.
2. **Model-to-model comparison:** We conduct a systematic evaluation of SurpriseLSTM against two benchmarks: IDyOM and the audio-based AudioIC model. We use four complementary paradigms: large-scale correlations on monophonic Western melodies, two-note interval pleasantness ratings, surprise profile fits on Bach chorales, and a replication of the musical Wundt effect.
3. **Musical context analysis:** Investigate how SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM respond differently to authentic cadences versus non-cadence contexts. By com-

paring scale degree distributions. We identify where neural and statistical approaches diverge in their understanding of tonal expectations.

1.5 Methodological overview

Our approach involves three main components: developing a neural network model of musical surprise, comparing it with existing models, and testing all models against human data.

We create SurpriseLSTM, a neural network that learns to predict the next note in a melody. The model uses basic musical information from each note (pitch, timing, melodic intervals, etc) and learns patterns from large collections of melodies. We compare this neural approach with two existing models: IDyOM (a statistical model) and AudioIC (which works with audio recordings).

To evaluate how well these models capture human musical expectations, we conduct five different tests:

- Finding the most important musical features for predicting surprise
- Comparing model predictions across large collections of Western melodies
- Testing whether models match human ratings of how pleasant different musical intervals sound
- Examining detailed surprise patterns in two Bach chorales that have human annotations
- Testing the *Wundt effect*, the idea that moderately surprising music is most pleasant

1.6 Contributions

1. We introduce **SurpriseLSTM**, a neural network model that applies statistical learning and probabilistic prediction principles to melodic expectation,

demonstrating that recurrent architectures can effectively model musical surprise from basic note-level features. Code and a pretrained model are made publicly available at <https://github.com/lissenko/surprise-lstm>.

2. We provide the first systematic comparison between neural and symbolic expectancy models across multiple behavioral and corpus-based benchmarks in the monophonic domain.
3. We identify key differences in how neural and statistical models distribute uncertainty and respond to musical contexts, particularly in cadential versus non-cadential situations.

1.7 Thesis Organization

This thesis is organized as follows.

Chapter 2 reviews the state of the art in computational models of musical expectations, covering statistical-learning and probabilistic-prediction hypotheses, rule-based approaches, symbolic information-theoretic approaches (e.g. IDyOM), and recent neural sequence models.

Chapter 3 describes the corpora and stimuli used throughout, details our MIDI preprocessing pipeline, and defines the note-level feature representations that serve as inputs to the developed model.

Chapter 4 presents the SurpriseLSTM architecture and training procedure. We explain the packed-sequence masking, the stacked LSTM layers, and the hyperparameters giving the most accurate pitch-prediction distributions.

Chapter 5 contains our five evaluation experiments, comparing SurpriseLSTM, IDyOM, and the audio-based AudioIC model on large-scale Western-melody correlations, two-note pleasantness ratings, detailed Bach-chorale surprise profiles, and a replication of the musical Wundt effect.

Chapter 6 probes the qualitative differences between SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM surprise distributions, showing how each model’s uncertainty and context-sensitivity diverge, and discusses these findings in light of the SLH and PPH framework and alternative cognitive hypotheses.

Chapter 7 concludes with a summary of contributions, discussion of limitations, and an outline of directions for future work.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Musical Expectation, Surprise, and Uncertainty

Before examining computational models, we must clarify the key psychological concepts underlying musical expectation. Huron's comprehensive framework distinguishes between several temporal phases of expectation [1]:

Pre-outcome emotions arise from the expectation itself: anticipation creates tension before an event occurs. Prediction responses reflect the cognitive assessment of what will happen next. Reaction responses occur immediately when the expected or unexpected event arrives. Appraisal responses involve the conscious evaluation of whether the outcome was positive or negative.

Musical surprise occurs when an actual musical event deviates from what was predicted. Following information theory, surprise can be quantified as the negative log-probability of an event: highly probable events yield low surprise, while improbable events produce high surprise. This connects to the concept of information content [21]: surprising events carry more information than predictable ones.

Uncertainty refers to the spread of the predictive distribution: when many different continuations seem equally likely, uncertainty is high; when one continuation dominates, uncertainty is low. Importantly, uncertainty and surprise are distinct: a

highly uncertain situation can yield low surprise if the actual outcome was among the many expected possibilities.

This framework reveals why computational modeling matters: if human musical cognition operates through statistical prediction, then successful models should capture both the central tendencies (what listeners expect most) and the uncertainty distributions (how confident those expectations are).

2.2 Musical Style as Probabilistic Grammar

A musical style embodies the characteristic constraints and patterns of a cultural tradition. In Meyer's view, these constraints function as a probabilistic grammar that governs which note-to-note transitions are permissible or likely within that style [2]. Listeners internalize this grammar through exposure, forming cognitive expectations that guide perception, emotion, and communication between composer, performer, and audience. Alterations to the learned grammar shift what listeners perceive as normal or surprising.

Modeling melodic perception thus requires two components: (1) acquisition of the style's probabilistic grammar, and (2) a mechanism for generating predictions (and surprisal) from that grammar. In this chapter, we review major approaches to these problems, beginning with classic rule-based theories and progressing to modern statistical and deep-learning models.

2.3 Rule-Based Expectation: Implication-Realization

The Implication-Realization (I-R) theory, originating with Meyer and formalized by Narmour [3], posits that each melodic interval carries an *implicative* force (predicting a likely continuation) while certain intervals are *realized* when they confirm or resolve prior expectations. Narmour's computational model encodes a small set of symbolic rules that approximate listeners' bottom-up, Gestalt-based inferences:

Registrational Direction Small intervals tend to continue in the same direction; large

leaps imply an upcoming reversal of direction.

Intervallic Difference Successive intervals of similar magnitude are expected after small leaps; large leaps imply a subsequent smaller step.

Registrat Return After a directional change, the melody often returns toward the pitch region of the preceding note.

Proximity Very small intervals (up to five semitones) imply continuation in the same direction, with strength varying by size.

Closure A combination of direction change and interval-size reduction signals the end of a melodic unit.

While I-R explains many perceptual phenomena, its fixed rules require manual tuning and do not adapt automatically to diverse musical styles or capture higher-order statistics.

2.4 Probabilistic Rule-Based Approaches

The rigid determinism of early rule-based theories led to hybrid approaches combining symbolic rules with probabilistic mechanisms. Temperley's Bayesian model of melody perception [22] exemplifies this bridge between rule-based and statistical approaches.

Temperley's model incorporates three probabilistic principles: melodies stay within narrow pitch ranges, note-to-note intervals tend to be small (pitch proximity), and pitches conform to key-dependent distributions. Using Bayesian inference, the model simultaneously infers key and evaluates melody probability through combined range, proximity, and key profiles.

However, the approach still requires manual specification of profile parameters and musical knowledge encoding. While more flexible than purely symbolic systems, it cannot automatically discover relevant features or adapt to novel musical styles without expert intervention.

2.5 IDyOM: Information Dynamics of Music

The Information Dynamics of Music (IDyOM; [7, 8]) is a symbolic statistical model that unifies the Statistical Learning Hypothesis and the Probabilistic Prediction Hypothesis in a single framework for monophonic melodies. IDyOM estimates conditional pitch probabilities via a variable-order Markov mechanism with *prediction by partial matching* (PPM*), integrates multiple musical features through *viewpoints*, and balances long-term and short-term memory models.

2.5.1 Variable-order PPM* inference

A fixed-order n -gram model assigns zero probability to unseen n -grams, making surprisal undefined. PPM* overcomes this by interpolating across all shorter context lengths, allocating nonzero probability mass to novel sequences [23]. Formally, the PPM* estimate is

$$P_{\text{PPM}^*}(e | c) = \sum_{k=0}^{|c|} \lambda_k P_{\text{ML}}(e | c_{|c|-k+1}^{|c|}),$$

where P_{ML} is the maximum-likelihood estimate on the last k symbols of context c , and weights $\{\lambda_k\}$ ensure a smooth back-off.

2.5.2 Multiple Viewpoint Integration

Music contains orthogonal dimensions such as pitch interval, scale degree, duration ratio and metrical position. IDyOM constructs a separate PPM* model for each *viewpoint* $v \in V$, yielding distributions $P_v(e | c)$. To fuse these, each viewpoint is weighted by its relative confidence (lower entropy) at that timestep (see Figure 1):

$$w_v = (1 - H(P_v)/H_{\max}(v))^{-1} \quad , \quad P(e | c) = \frac{\sum_{v \in V} w_v P_v(e | c)}{\sum_{v \in V} w_v} \quad ,$$

where $H(P_v) = -\sum_e P_v(e) \log_2 P_v(e)$ and $H_{\max}(v) = \log_2 |\mathcal{E}_v|$ is the maximum entropy over viewpoint v 's alphabet \mathcal{E}_v .

2.5.3 Short-term and Long-term Memory

To reflect both lifelong enculturation and piece-specific context, IDyOM maintains *long-term model* (LTM) trained on a large corpus of melodies, and *short-term model* (STM) built dynamically on the current piece. Their predictions are interpolated, again by entropy weighting, to return the final $P(e | c)$.

2.6 Deep Learning Approaches

2.6.1 Information-Content Curve Matching (IIC)

Bjare *et al.* [25] propose a method for steering symbolic music generation by matching an *Instantaneous Information Content* (IIC) curve to a user-specified target. Given any autoregressive critic model p , they compute each token's surprisal

$$\text{IC}(x_i | x_{<i}) = -\log p(x_i | x_{<i})$$

and then project these discrete IC values onto real time via a temporal-localization function $f(i, x)$ and a smooth window λ , yielding the continuous IIC curve

$$\text{IIC}(t, x) = \sum_{f(i, x) < t} \lambda(t - f(i, x), i) \text{IC}(x_i | x_{<i}).$$

To guide generation, they define the L^1 deviation between the generated IIC and a target curve $\text{IIC}^*(t)$,

$$\|\text{IIC} - \text{IIC}^*\|_1 = \int_0^T |\text{IIC}(t) - \text{IIC}^*(t, x)| dt,$$

and employ beam search over continuations, selecting at each step the candidate whose IIC best matches the target.

In their experiments, they instantiate p as a causal Transformer *PIA* model [26]

Figure 1: High-level architecture of IDyOM. Multiple viewpoint streams feed PPM* engines in both long-term and short-term modules. Their weighted outputs combine to produce the final conditional distribution. [24]

built on the Perceiver IO architecture, pretrained on a large corpus of expressive piano performances. MIDI events are tokenized into Pitch, Velocity, Duration, and Timeshift tokens; the Transformer predicts the next token’s distribution at each step, yielding the conditional probabilities used for IC. They demonstrate that (1) IIC correlates strongly with harmonic and rhythmic complexity, (2) listener studies can reliably identify which target IIC curve was used, and (3) matching IIC enables control of surprisal in symbolic music generation.

Importantly, the underlying PIA model is not publicly released, and key implementation details are not sufficiently documented for independent reimplementa-tion. As a result, while the IIC framework itself is general, we cannot directly reproduce or compare its performance with our SurpriseLSTM in open-source settings.

2.6.2 AudioIC: Surprisal from Audio

Bjare *et al.* [27] extend surprisal estimation to raw music recordings by training a 12-layer causal Transformer to autoregressively predict 64-dimensional latent audio frames obtained from the Music2Latent [28] consistency autoencoder [29]. Instead of a softmax over a discrete vocabulary, they model the next-frame distribution as a 32-component Gaussian mixture whose parameters (means, variances, weights) are produced by the Transformer’s final linear layer. The frame-wise information content

$$\text{IC}(x_t | x_{<t}) = -\log p_{\text{GMM}}(x_t | x_{<t})$$

is thus unbounded and reflects surprise over continuous audio representations.

They train on a large multi-stem popular-music corpus, fine-tuning on vocal stems when modeling EEG responses. Positional context is captured via rotary embeddings and FlashAttention. Audio is preprocessed into mono MP3 at 22 050 Hz, encoded by Music2Latent at approximately 11 Hz frame rate, and concatenated into sequences up to 4600 frames (about 7 min).

In evaluation, AudioIC’s mean IC decreases reliably on repeated segments and rises on contrasting segments later in a piece. Moreover, including AudioIC estimates in

a cortical-tracking regression significantly improves EEG prediction over an energy-only baseline, demonstrating that AudioIC captures neural surprisal signatures.

The authors provide an open-source implementation and pretrained weights, enabling reproduction of key results.

2.6.3 Diffusion-Based Surprisal Estimation

Two distinct approaches have emerged for estimating musical surprisal using diffusion models, each addressing different aspects of temporal musical prediction.

Masclef and Keller [30] propose using a denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) as a deep generative measure of musical expectation. They treat a diffusion model’s variational bound on data likelihood as an approximate surprisal:

$$-\log p_{\theta}(x_0) \leq \underbrace{L_T}_{\approx 0} + \sum_{t=1}^T (L_{t-1} - L_0),$$

where each L_t is expressed in closed form via the model’s predicted noise $\hat{\epsilon}_{\theta}(x_t, t)$. They apply a pretrained `audio-diffusion-256` model trained on mel-spectrograms, computing total surprisal by summing likelihood bounds across non-overlapping 5-second blocks. Using the Gold *et al.* corpus, they demonstrate that diffusion-based surprisal exhibits the expected Wundt effect with significant quadratic relationships between information content and listener preference.

On the other hand, Bjare *et al.* [31] extend surprisal estimation to causal, autoregressive scenarios using autoregressive diffusion models (ADMs). Unlike approaches that assume Gaussian mixture distributions for next-step predictions, their method estimates information content through the instantaneous change of variables formula applied to probability flow ODEs. They employ two diffusion processes: EDM and Rectified Flow, to estimate surprisal in the Music2Latent continuous audio representation space.

An important insight from their work is that diffusion models can compute likelihood estimates at different noise levels during the denoising process, potentially

capturing musical features at varying temporal and spectral granularities. They demonstrate that intermediate noise levels better correlate with symbolic pitch surprisal (as measured by IDyOM) than fully denoised representations, suggesting that controlled noise filtering preserves pitch-related expectation while removing timbral variations irrelevant to melodic surprise.

Chapter 3

Dataset, Preprocessing, and Feature Representation

This chapter surveys the monophonic MIDI corpora employed in our study, details the preprocessing steps applied to each collection, and outlines the full set of melodic features, along with their domains and encoding schemes, used by our LSTM model.

3.1 Monophonic MIDI Corpora

Table 1 lists the MIDI datasets we used, each serving a different role (training, validation or testing). Although all collections are meant to be monophonic, a few files may contain overlapping notes; these are removed during our preprocessing step. We will explain how and when we use each set in Chapters 4 and 5. Each dataset is labeled with an integer ID, which will be used for all subsequent references.

The Clean Melodies collection [32] is a hand-picked subset of the larger Los Angeles MIDI dataset. From that master corpus, which itself merges the Lakh midi dataset [33], the MetaMIDI Dataset [34], Reddit MIDI and other public scrapes, it uses only the files containing a single, strictly monophonic melody track or channel. Each melody was extracted directly from its MIDI file (no audio source), and no further transformations or post-processing were applied beyond the monophony filter. This

Table 1: Overview of Datasets

ID	Description	Melodies	Events	E/M	Pitches
1	Clean melodies (Tegridy-MIDI-Dataset)	117 659	7 530 176	64.0	79
2	Western melodies	1 110	50 936	45.9	37
	Chorale melodies	338	16 912	50.0	24
	German folk songs	213	8 393	39.4	27
	Canadian folk ballads	152	8 552	56.3	26
	Yugoslavian folk songs	119	2 691	22.6	25
	Austrian folk songs	104	5 306	51.0	35
	Swiss folk songs	93	4 586	49.3	34
	Alsatian folk songs	91	4 496	49.4	32
3	Naturalistic stimuli	57	4 590	80.5	48
4	Interval pleasantness	31	62	2.0	31
5	Manzara experiment stimuli	2	86	43.0	12
6	AC/NC stimuli	90	754	8.4	28

clean subset provides a compact, high-quality set of MIDI melodies for initial model development and feature testing.

The Western melodies corpus combines several public-domain collections originally distributed in `**kern` format by the Music Cognition Laboratory at Ohio State University (see <https://kern.humdrum.org/cgi-bin/browse?l=essen/europa>) and the Centre for Computer Assisted Research in the Humanities at Stanford University (see <https://kern.ccarh.org/cgi-bin/ksbrowse?s=nova>). It was assembled to capture the broad Occidental melodic tradition, spanning repertoires from Europe and a small selection from North America.

The Naturalistic Stimuli corpus [35] was developed to probe listeners' aesthetic responses by presenting excerpts drawn from a broad array of musical genres, periods, composers, tonalities, and meters. Participants heard each excerpt and provided ratings of perceived pleasantness/liking.

The interval pleasantness corpus is derived from a dense rating experiment by Anglada-Tort *et al.* [36], in which 415 U.S. participants rated the pleasantness of pitch intervals, derived from 15,000 stimuli sampled randomly and uniformly from -15 to $+15$ semitones. They used a pleasantness scale (1 = not at all pleasant to 7 = very much pleasant). We retained only integer-valued semitone intervals, i.e. those whose size is an exact whole number of semitones (no fractional values). We then generated 31 two-note MIDI files, each beginning on the reference pitch C4 and spanning all integer semitone intervals from -15 to $+15$.

The Manzara corpus [37] comprises two monophonic lines extracted from J.S. Bach chorales (see Figure 3). In the original behavioral study, participants were asked to place monetary wagers on the identity of each upcoming pitch. From their trial-by-trial wagering accuracy, the information content (IC) of each note was estimated, yielding entropy profiles for the melodies. Further details of the entropy computation and our analyses are presented in Chapter 5.

The AC/NC stimuli corpus is derived from the melodic cloze experiment by Morgan *et al.* [38], in which participants heard monophonic melodic openings and were

asked to sing the note they expected to come next. The corpus comprises 45 pairs of melodic stems, where each pair consists of an Authentic Cadence (AC) version and a Non-Cadence (NC) version that differ by only a small number of notes. AC condition melodies end with an implied V harmony (dominant chord) that creates a strong expectation for resolution to the tonic (scale degree 1), while NC condition melodies do not end on a V harmony and were designed to avoid creating strong expectations for any particular continuation note. Although monophonic, these melodies reliably generate implicit harmonic structure for Western listeners. The corpus provides a controlled test case for examining how computational models handle cadential versus non-cadential melodic contexts, particularly their ability to recognize one of the most foundational harmonic progressions in Western music.

3.2 Preprocessing of MIDI Stimuli

Before fitting any models or computing surprise metrics, every MIDI file is processed through the following pipeline.

Parsing and feature extraction Each file is loaded with `pretty_midi` and converted into a sequence of per-note feature vectors (see Table 2).

Fingerprinting and deduplication We compute a *fingerprint* by concatenating the pitch-duration pairs of the first ten notes of each melody. Any melody whose fingerprint matches a previously seen one is discarded.

Monophony and length filtering Melodies that are not strictly monophonic (i.e. contain overlapping notes) or whose total note count falls below a dataset-specific minimum are removed. This threshold is chosen depending of the nature of the data.

Shuffling The remaining melodies are randomly permuted to eliminate ordering biases during training and evaluation.

IDyOM-only subset In parallel, we assemble a secondary corpus for IDyOM evaluation by reapplying all steps above and additionally excluding any melody containing notes shorter than a sixty-fourth duration (to avoid a specific runtime error with IDyOM).

3.3 Feature Representation

In order to feed each melody into the neural sequence model, every note is converted into a fixed-length vector whose components encode melodic, rhythmic, and tonal attributes. Most of the features implemented here are drawn from the cognitively motivated set used in the IDyOM model [7], which were designed to capture perceptually salient aspects of melodic structure.

Causality constraint. One crucial requirement is that no feature may use information from notes that occur later than the one being encoded. Since our goal is to model human listeners’ surprise in real time, each feature for the t -th note is computed solely from the first t notes (and any global metadata such as inferred key); the model never peeks ahead at future events it has not yet heard. This causal restriction ensures that computed surprise truly reflects what a listener could know at each moment in the unfolding melody.

Table 2 summarizes the full set of features, their mathematical domains, and the form of their encoding.

The most fundamental attribute is the `pitch` of each note, represented as an integer MIDI value in $\{0, \dots, 127\}$ and embedded via a 128-dimensional one-hot vector. To capture octave-invariant patterns, we also record `pitch_class`, i.e. the pitch modulo 12, similarly encoded as a 12-dimensional one-hot vector. Melodic motion is described both by the signed `interval` from the preceding note (an integer in $\{-36, \dots, 36\}$) and by its `contour` (the sign of that interval in $\{-1, 0, 1\}$), each discretized into a one-hot representation. A complementary feature, `cpintfip`, measures the signed distance from the first note of the melody, again as a one-hot vector over the same 73-value range.

Key-centric information is introduced via `scale degree` (an index in $\{0, \dots, 6\}$ corresponding to the inferred diatonic scale), a binary `key_membership` flag indicating whether the pitch belongs to the local key, and a binary `phrase` marker for phrase boundaries. None of these three features are directly present in raw MIDI data; they were therefore inferred using the `music21` toolkit, which may introduce extraction errors. Scale degree is one-hot encoded over 7 values, while key membership and phrase are each represented as a single binary indicator.

The overall pitch height is further abstracted into a three-level `register` (low, mid, high) and noted as a binary flag `is_repeated_pitch` if the same pitch occurred within the previous five notes.

Rhythmic location and duration are encoded through four continuous features: the note’s absolute `onset` time and its `duration`, each normalized by the maximum observed value; the *inter-onset interval* (`ioi`) between successive notes, again normalized; and the fractional `beat_position` within the current metrical beat, taking values in $[0, 1)$. We further discretize duration into a nominal `symbolic_duration` index (mapping to whole, half, quarter, dotted values, etc.) and annotate whether a note begins a new phrase via the `phrase` one-hot flag.

Taken together, these 15 features produce an input vector of dimension

$$D = \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \dim(f),$$

where \mathcal{F} is the chosen feature subset and each $\dim(f)$ is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Melodic Feature Domains and Encodings

Feature	Description	Domain	Encoding
pitch	MIDI pitch value	$\{0, \dots, 127\}$	one-hot vector
pitch_class	Pitch modulo octave	$\{0, \dots, 11\}$	one-hot vector
interval	Difference from previous pitch	$\{-36, \dots, 36\}$	one-hot vector
contour	Direction of melodic motion	$\{-1, 0, 1\}$	one-hot vector
cpintfip	Pitch relative to first note	$\{-36, \dots, 36\}$	one-hot vector
scale_degree	Degree in inferred key scale	$\{0, \dots, 6\}$	one-hot vector
key_membership	In-scale vs. out-of-scale flag	$\{0, 1\}$	binary value
register	Low/mid/high pitch register	$\{0, 1, 2\}$	one-hot vector
is_repeated_pitch	Repetition within recent window	$\{0, 1\}$	binary value
onset	Absolute start time of the note	$[0, O_{\max}]$	normalized scalar
duration	Note duration in seconds	$[0, D_{\max}]$	normalized scalar
symbolic_duration	Nearest nominal note type	$\{0, \dots, 20\}$	one-hot vector
ioi	Inter-onset interval	$[0, I_{\max}]$	normalized scalar
beat_position	Fractional location within the beat	$[0, 1)$	scalar
phrase	Phrase boundary marker	$\{0, 1\}$	one-hot vector

Chapter 4

Model Architecture and Training

4.1 Why Next-Pitch Prediction

In principle, one could train a model to predict human-reported surprise directly at each note. However, this would require a very large corpus of melodies annotated, at the note level, with subjective surprise ratings. Although small datasets of this kind exist (e.g. the two-melody Manzara corpus in Chapter 3), their size is far too limited to support the training of a high-capacity neural network. Instead, we exploit plentiful unannotated melodic data by framing the problem as next-pitch prediction, from which surprise (Information Content) is computed analytically.

4.2 Desired Model Behavior

Our goal is to construct a predictive model of melodic surprise that, given a sequence of note-level feature vectors

$$X = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_T] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times D},$$

outputs at each timestep t a probability distribution

$$p(\cdot \mid \mathbf{x}_{1:t}) \in \Delta^{127}$$

over the next pitch. From this distribution we compute the Information Content (IC) of the true next note,

$$\text{IC}(x_{t+1}) = -\log_2 p(x_{t+1} \mid \mathbf{x}_{1:t}),$$

which serves as our quantitative measure of surprise. In behavioral terms, the model should assign high probability mass to notes that human listeners expect, yet leave enough residual probability on other notes so that unexpected events yield a non-trivial IC (and thus a meaningful surprise).

4.3 Architectural Motivation

Because melodic surprise is inherently a function of conditional sequence prediction, our model must be *autoregressive*: each output distribution depends only on the past. We initially explored Transformer-style self-attention architectures, but found that they drive the predictive distribution to be overly peaked (very low entropy), assigning nearly all probability mass to a single most-likely pitch. While this yields low cross-entropy loss, it underestimates human-like fallibility: if the model is almost certain of the next note, then any deviation incurs an extreme IC, exaggerating surprise.

In contrast, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks naturally maintain wider uncertainty, distributing probability more evenly across plausible continuations. This broader distribution produces more realistic IC curves, avoids saturating surprise on every unexpected event, and leads to better correlations with human judgments (Chapter 5).

4.4 Data Input, Masking, and Packing

Each melody is a variable-length sequence of T notes, each represented by a D -dimensional feature vector. To train in minibatches we must align sequences of different lengths: we pad all sequences in a batch to the same maximum length T_{\max} , and record a binary mask $M \in \{0, 1\}^{B \times T_{\max}}$ indicating which timesteps are

real notes versus padding. Without masking, the model would learn from padding tokens, corrupting its predictions and wasting computation.

Once padded, we use PyTorch’s `pack_padded_sequence` to collapse out the padding dimension and feed only the real timesteps into the LSTM. Packing offers two key benefits: (1) it prevents the LSTM from performing useless updates on padding positions, saving compute and memory; and (2) it ensures that the hidden-state dynamics respect each sequence’s true length, avoiding bleed-through from padding. After the recurrent stack, we call `pad_packed_sequence` to restore the original time axis, re-insert padding, and re-apply the mask for any subsequent loss calculation.

4.5 SurpriseLSTM Architecture

The resulting *SurpriseLSTM* model, illustrated in Figure 2, processes each packed batch through a stack of three LSTM layers of hidden size H . The time-hidden tensor is then unpacked, regularized with dropout rate p , linearly projected to 128 logits, and normalized via softmax to return the predictive distribution over the next MIDI pitch.

4.6 Training Objective and Loss

We train the model to predict the next pitch at each timestep. Given a batch of sequences, let $\hat{P}_{t,i}$ be the model’s predicted probability of pitch i at time t , and let y_t be the true next-pitch index. We use the masked cross-entropy loss,

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{\sum_{t,i} M_{t,i}} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{128} M_{t,i} \mathbf{1}[i = y_t] \log \hat{P}_{t,i},$$

where $M_{t,i}$ zeros out all padding positions. This ensures that only real note predictions contribute to the loss. Gradients are clipped to norm 5 at each update to prevent exploding gradients, and parameters are optimized with Adam (learning rate 0.001).

During training each melody is shifted: the input at time t is \mathbf{x}_t , and the target is

Figure 2: Block diagram of the SurpriseLSTM forward pass. The input feature tensor (padded and masked) is packed into a variable-length sequence, processed by a 2-layer LSTM stack, unpacked back to the original time dimension, regularized by dropout, linearly projected to 128 pitch logits, and normalized via softmax.

the true pitch at $t + 1$. By minimizing this loss, the model learns to assign high probability to the actual continuation at every step, thereby capturing the statistical structure of melodic sequences.

Chapter 5

Experimental Validation

5.1 Experimental Methodology

In this chapter, we evaluate our SurpriseLSTM model of melodic surprise against two benchmarks: the statistical IDyOM model [7] and the audio-based AudioIC model [39]. We present five complementary analyses: (1) a greedy forward–backward feature-selection procedure to identify the most informative input representations; (2) a large-scale correlation study on a Western-melody corpus; (3) a two-note interval paradigm relating model-derived surprise to human pleasantness ratings; (4) detailed entropy profiles for two Bach chorales with human surprise data; and (5) a replication of the classic Wundt effect via mixed-effects modeling of surprise and liking.

Ideally, one would validate a surprise model by comparing its note-by-note predictions to human listeners’ surprise judgments. However, only two Bach chorales with such annotations are available [37], which is insufficient for broad generalization. To address this, we employ the different evaluation paradigms described above to build a comprehensive assessment of model performance.

5.2 Experiment 1: Incremental Feature Selection

To identify the subset of note-level features that best support the prediction of melodic surprise, we employed an alternating forward-backward greedy search. We begin with no features selected. In the forward pass, each candidate feature not yet in the set is added one at a time, the model is retrained, and the addition accepted as soon as it yields any improvement in performance; the pass then restarts from this enlarged set. If no single addition improves performance, we enter the backward pass: each feature in the current set is removed in turn, and any removal that boosts performance is accepted, after which we return to the forward pass. This alternating process continues until neither adding nor removing any single feature yields further gains.

All evaluations use the two chorale melodies from the Manzara experiment (Dataset 5, Figure 3), with human-rated information-content profiles [37]. Each candidate feature set is used to train three independent runs of the SurpriseLSTM model on our clean melodies training corpus (Dataset 1), and tested only on these two chorales to measure generalization to unseen material.

(a) BWV 379: *Meinen Jesum laß ich nicht, Jesus*

(b) BWV 159: *Jesu Leiden, Pein und Tod*

Figure 3: Score excerpts for the two Bach chorales used in the Manzara experiment (Dataset 5).

In every run, the SurpriseLSTM consists of a stack of two LSTM layers, each with

hidden size $H = 1024$, followed by dropout ($p = 0.5$) and a final linear projection to 128 pitch logits (see Chapter 4). Models are trained for 8 epochs with batch size 128, using the Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.001), and gradients clipped to norm 5. These values were selected after exploring a range of hidden sizes, dropout rates, learning rates, and training durations: they provided the best trade-off between model capacity and generalization, yielding stable convergence across random seeds without evident overfitting.

Table 3 gives metrics at each stage of the search, including Spearman’s correlation ρ_s , mean information content H , adjusted R^2 , regression slope b , and training/test losses. We performed the greedy forward–backward selection once targeting maximization of ρ_s . We chose Spearman’s correlation over Pearson’s as we expect monotonic rather than linear relations in the IC pairs.

The inverse relationship, where mean IC H falls as Spearman ρ_s rises, aligns with theories of efficient cognitive encoding: listeners may favor features that boost the expectedness of events (raising r) while simultaneously compressing redundant information (lowering H) [40, 41].

Table 3: Incremental Feature Selection Results for SurpriseLSTM Model

Features Added	ρ_s	H	R_{adj}^2	b	Train Loss	Test Loss
pitch (baseline)	0.628	2.065	0.468	0.572	1.712	1.450
+ duration	0.637	2.003	0.490	0.629	1.664	1.401
+ symbolic duration	0.638	2.030	0.472	0.647	1.659	1.429
+ onset	0.650	2.007	0.464	0.598	1.652	1.407
+ interval	0.650	1.996	0.454	0.630	1.609	1.397
+ contour	0.665	1.976	0.473	0.628	1.601	1.391
+ ioi	0.667	1.987	0.469	0.606	1.597	1.396

The results in Table 3 demonstrate systematic improvements in the model’s ability to predict human surprise as successive features are incorporated. Starting with only the `pitch` feature as baseline, SurpriseLSTM achieves a Spearman correlation of $\rho_s = 0.628$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.468$, with a mean entropy of 2.065 bits. Adding `duration` increases correlation to $\rho_s = 0.637$ and $R_{\text{adj}}^2 = 0.490$ while reducing mean

entropy to 2.003 bits, indicating that rhythmic information enhances both predictive accuracy and model efficiency.

Incorporating `symbolic duration` (nearest notated value) maintains the correlation gain ($\rho_s = 0.638$) but shows a slight decrease in R_{adj}^2 to 0.472, suggesting some redundancy with the continuous duration feature. The addition of `onset` timing produces a more substantial improvement, boosting correlation to $\rho_s = 0.650$ while maintaining mean entropy around 2.007 bits. Adding `interval` information maintains this correlation level while further reducing entropy to 1.996 bits, demonstrating more efficient encoding of melodic relationships.

The inclusion of `contour` features yields the most significant improvement in correlation ($\rho_s = 0.665$) and continues the trend of reduced mean entropy (1.976 bits), indicating that melodic shape information captures important aspects of human expectation. Finally, incorporating `ioi` (inter-onset interval) provides a modest additional gain to $\rho_s = 0.667$ and $R_{\text{adj}}^2 = 0.469$, with mean entropy stabilizing at 1.987 bits.

Overall, the incremental addition of these six additional features results in modest improvements from the pitch-only baseline ($\Delta\rho_s = +0.039$, $\Delta R_{\text{adj}}^2 = +0.001$) while achieving more efficient representation ($\Delta H = -0.078$ bits). This suggests that pitch information alone captures much of the structure underlying human musical expectation, with additional temporal and melodic features providing incremental refinements. The consistent reduction in both training and test loss (from 1.712 to 1.597 and 1.450 to 1.396, respectively) confirms that while these supplementary features do enhance model performance, the core predictive power derives primarily from pitch relationships.

The dominance of pitch information in predicting human melodic surprise requires careful interpretation. While the baseline pitch feature alone captures substantial variance, this finding encompasses not merely raw pitch values but the rich array of pitch-derived relationships that the neural model learns to encode in its distributed representations. The model weights implicitly capture complex interactions between

absolute pitch, relative intervals, scale degrees, contour patterns, and their temporal dependencies: relationships that extend far beyond simple note identification. In essence, the `pitch` baseline represents a compressed encoding of melodic structure that encompasses many of the derived features we explicitly tested.

This dominance of pitch-related information raises intriguing questions about the universality of these findings. While pitch relationships capture the majority of variance in our Western musical context, this pattern might differ substantially in other cultural traditions where rhythmic complexity plays a more central role in musical structure and expectation. For instance, in many African, Indian, or Middle Eastern musical traditions, rhythmic patterns and their variations constitute primary sources of musical tension and resolution. A cross-cultural extension of this feature selection analysis could reveal whether the relative importance of pitch versus temporal features varies systematically across musical cultures, potentially uncovering important differences in how different societies organize musical expectation.

5.3 Experiment 2: Model-Model Correlations

To situate SurpriseLSTM among existing approaches, we computed three sets of note-by-note surprise correlations on the same 1110-melody Western corpus (Dataset 2): (1) SurpriseLSTM vs. IDyOM, (2) SurpriseLSTM vs. AudioIC, and (3) IDyOM vs. AudioIC. IDyOM was retrained on our primary MIDI collection (Dataset 1) using the `cpintfip` viewpoint together with the linked `cpintfref`⊗`dur-ratio` combination shown by Pearce [7] to best predict pitch expectancy. SurpriseLSTM employed the feature subset selected in Experiment 1. AudioIC, which operates on continuous audio rather than symbolic sequences, was applied to WAV renders of each MIDI file (synthesized using the Upright Piano KW SoundFont available at <https://freepats.zenvoid.org/Piano/acoustic-grand-piano.html>). Because AudioIC’s output is a continuous time-series of surprise values, we sampled its curve at the onset times of each MIDI note to obtain discrete note-level estimates. Moreover, AudioIC incorporates timbral features since it uses audio, absent from both SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM, so some systematic differences are to be expected.

For each melody, we extracted surprise time-series from all three models and computed Spearman’s rank correlation ρ_s , and fitted a simple linear regression to obtain the slope b and the adjusted coefficient of determination R_{adj}^2 . We then averaged each metric across melodies and report the mean \pm SE in Table 4.

Table 4: Inter-Model Correlation Statistics Across 1,110 Western Melodies

Model Pair	$\rho_s \pm \text{SE}$	$b \pm \text{SE}$	$R_{\text{adj}}^2 \pm \text{SE}$
IDyOM vs SurpriseLSTM	0.639 ± 0.135	0.517 ± 0.187	0.411 ± 0.166
AudioIC vs SurpriseLSTM	0.300 ± 0.163	0.035 ± 0.017	0.131 ± 0.121
AudioIC vs IDyOM	0.480 ± 0.151	4.704 ± 1.298	0.323 ± 0.150

SurpriseLSTM shows the strongest correspondence with IDyOM ($\rho_s = 0.639 \pm 0.135$, $R_{\text{adj}}^2 = 0.411 \pm 0.166$), confirming that our neural model effectively captures the conditional pitch expectations characteristic of symbolic, information-theoretic prediction. This substantial correlation suggests both models tap into similar aspects of musical structure despite their totally different computational architectures.

In contrast, AudioIC exhibits weaker correlations with both symbolic models: $\rho_s = 0.300 \pm 0.163$ with SurpriseLSTM and $\rho_s = 0.480 \pm 0.151$ with IDyOM. These lower correlations likely reflect AudioIC’s design for arbitrary audio content, including polyphonic textures and timbral nuances, whereas IDyOM and SurpriseLSTM operate strictly on monophonic, symbolic representations. The moderate AudioIC–IDyOM correlation ($R_{\text{adj}}^2 = 0.323 \pm 0.150$) suggests some shared sensitivity to melodic patterns, though filtered through AudioIC’s distinct spectro-temporal processing.

5.4 Experiment 3: Surprise vs. Pleasantness

For a direct behavioral validation of our model, we compared SurpriseLSTM’s information-content estimates against human pleasantness ratings for isolated pitch intervals (Dataset 4). These ratings were collected in a *dense rating* paradigm [36], in which 415 US participants judged 15 000 instances of two-note stimuli spanning the integer interval range $[-15, +15]$ semitones. Participants provided mean pleasantness ratings on a 1 (not at all) to 7 (very much) scale. We extracted the smoothed

mean and standard error values for each integer interval.

We applied the same SurpriseLSTM model (features, training data, viewpoints and hyperparameters) as in Experiment 2. For each integer interval $\Delta \in [-15, 15]$, we synthesized a two-note MIDI file in which a fixed reference pitch (C_5) is followed by $C_5 + \Delta$ after 0.5 s. We then predicted the information content (IC) of the second note from SurpriseLSTM, from IDyOM (using the same viewpoints and training set), and from AudioIC (after rendering each MIDI to WAV and sampling AudioIC’s continuous surprise curve at the note onset times). Finally, we computed Spearman’s correlations between model IC and human pleasantness across the 31 integer intervals.

Table 5: Correlation between Model Information Content and Human Pleasantness Ratings

Model	Correlation (ρ)	Significance
SurpriseLSTM	-0.821	$p < .001^{***}$
IDyOM	-0.802	$p < .001^{***}$
AudioIC	+0.240	$p = .19$

The correlations in Table 5 show that both SurpriseLSTM ($\rho = -0.821$, $p < .001$) and IDyOM ($\rho = -0.802$, $p < .001$) exhibit strong negative correlations with pleasantness ratings, indicating that higher model-predicted surprise corresponds to lower listener preferences. Both symbolic models capture the human tendency to find highly unexpected musical events less pleasant.

AudioIC shows no reliable relationship with pleasantness ratings ($\rho = +0.240$, $p = .19$). This lack of correlation may reflect AudioIC’s focus on spectro-temporal features that do not align with the mechanisms underlying aesthetic preference in melodic contexts.

These results indicate that symbolic, information-theoretic approaches to modeling melodic expectation capture the relationship between predictability and musical preference, where excessive surprise reduces listener satisfaction. The similar findings across SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM support expectation-based theories of

musical preference.

5.5 Experiment 4: Chorale Entropy Profiles

In this analysis we examine how well each model captures the surprise trajectory in two Bach chorales from the Manzara corpus (Dataset 5). These melodies, *Meinen Jesum laß ich nicht, Jesus* (BWV 379) and *Jesu Leiden, Pein und Tod* (BWV 159), are labeled with human IC profiles obtained in a behavioral study [37]. We apply the same SurpriseLSTM and the two benchmarks, IDyOM and AudioIC, to these chorales with the same parameters as in experiments 2 and 4.

Table 6 reports Spearman’s correlation ρ_s , mean IC, regression slope b , adjusted R^2 and test loss where available. The accompanying surprise over time trajectories are shown in Figure 4.

Table 6: Model Performance Metrics by Melody

Melody	Model	ρ_s	Mean IC	b	R_{adj}^2	Test Loss
BWV 379	SurpriseLSTM	0.698	2.070	0.635	0.541	1.435
	IDyOM	0.581	2.710	0.551	0.439	N/A
	AudioIC	0.384	24.263	0.033	0.120	N/A
BWV 159	SurpriseLSTM	0.663	2.049	0.504	0.360	1.421
	IDyOM	0.534	2.471	0.510	0.306	N/A
	AudioIC	0.283	25.221	0.030	0.096	N/A

The results in Table 6 show that SurpriseLSTM achieves the strongest alignment with human information content ratings on both chorales, with Spearman correlations of $\rho_s = 0.698$ (BWV 379) and $\rho_s = 0.663$ (BWV 159), and corresponding R_{adj}^2 values of 0.541 and 0.360 respectively. IDyOM performs comparably, with correlations of $\rho_s = 0.581$ and $\rho_s = 0.534$ for the two chorales, reflecting its effectiveness at symbolic pitch prediction. AudioIC shows weaker agreement with human ratings, achieving correlations of only $\rho_s = 0.384$ (BWV 379) and $\rho_s = 0.283$ (BWV 159).

Both symbolic models demonstrate consistent performance across the two chorales, with SurpriseLSTM maintaining a slight advantage in capturing human expectation

patterns. The lower regression slopes for AudioIC ($b = 0.033$ and $b = 0.030$) indicate a weaker linear relationship with human ratings compared to the symbolic approaches.

Figure 4: Comparison of human-derived Information Content (blue) and SurpriseLSTM predictions (red) for the two Manzara chorale stimuli (Dataset 5).

SurpriseLSTM’s superior performance on both Bach chorales merits deeper examination, as it suggests important differences in how neural and statistical models process musical information. Several factors may contribute to this advantage. First, SurpriseLSTM may capture more human-like probability distributions by learning distributed representations that naturally encode uncertainty in ways that align with human cognitive processing. Unlike IDyOM’s discrete viewpoint combinations, the neural model’s continuous hidden states may better approximate the nature of human musical expectations.

Second, the generalization advantage may reflect architectural differences in handling stylistic diversity. Bach chorales represent a highly specific musical style that differs significantly from much of the training corpus. SurpriseLSTM’s distributed representations may enable better transfer learning to unseen musical styles compared to IDyOM’s reliance on handcrafted viewpoint combinations optimized for particular statistical regularities. This suggests that neural approaches may offer superior robustness when encountering musical materials that deviate from training distributions. It is an important consideration for real-world applications where musical diversity is the norm rather than the exception.

5.6 Experiment 5: Wundt-Effect Modeling

The Wundt effect, first articulated by Berlyne [42], describes an inverted U-shaped relationship between stimulus complexity and pleasure, such that listeners prefer stimuli of intermediate complexity and find very low or very high complexity less enjoyable. In the musical domain, Gold et al. [35] operationalized complexity via the mean duration-weighted information content (mDW-IC) of a piece:

$$\text{mDW-IC} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T d_t [-\log_2 p(x_t | x_{1:t-1})]}{\sum_{t=1}^T d_t},$$

where x_t is the pitch at time t , d_t its duration, and the conditional probability $p(x_t | x_{1:t-1})$ is estimated by IDyOM using the `ioi-ratio` and `cpitch` viewpoints shown by Gold et al. [35] to best predict pitch expectancy.

Gold et al. applied this measure to 57 naturalistic, monophonic stimuli (Dataset 3), each rated for overall liking by 44 participants, and found significant negative linear and quadratic effects of standardized mDW-IC (zIC and zIC^2) on liking, confirming the Wundt effect in music listening.

We replicate their analysis using our SurpriseLSTM model to compute mDW-IC for the same 57 stimuli and we use their original human liking ratings. Table 7 reports the regression coefficients for both IDyOM and SurpriseLSTM, where the dependent variable is the participant’s liking rating and predictors are the standardized surprise zIC and its square zIC^2 .

Table 7: Wundt-effect model coefficients for IDyOM and SurpriseLSTM.

Parameter	IDyOM			SurpriseLSTM		
	Estimate	SE	p	Estimate	SE	p
Intercept	4.312	0.1100	$p < .001$	4.292	0.1103	$p < .001$
zIC	-0.218	0.0459	$p < .001$	-0.343	0.0449	$p < .001$
zIC^2	-0.095	0.0202	$p < .001$	-0.071	0.0196	$p = .003$
R_{adj}^2	0.2621			0.2860		

The results in Table 7 confirm the presence of the Wundt effect in both models. Most importantly, both IDyOM and SurpriseLSTM show significant negative quadratic coefficients (zIC^2 : -0.095 , $p < .001$ and -0.071 , $p = .003$ respectively), which is the evidence for the inverted U-shaped relationship between information content and pleasantness. This negative curvature indicates that pleasantness initially increases with moderate surprise but then decreases as surprise becomes excessive, consistent with Wundt’s arousal-preference theory.

The significant negative linear coefficients (zIC : -0.218 for IDyOM, -0.343 for SurpriseLSTM, both $p < .001$) combined with the negative quadratic terms create the characteristic inverted U-shape. SurpriseLSTM exhibits a stronger linear effect than IDyOM, suggesting it captures a more pronounced relationship between information content and preference judgments.

SurpriseLSTM also explains slightly more variance in pleasantness ratings ($R_{adj}^2 =$

0.286 vs. 0.262 for IDyOM), indicating that the neural model captures the complexity-pleasure relationship at least as effectively as the established symbolic benchmark.

5.7 Summary and Discussion

Across five complementary evaluations, the SurpriseLSTM model demonstrates consistent ability to predict human melodic surprise. Our forward-backward feature selection analysis revealed that seven cognitively motivated features (`pitch`, `duration`, `symbolic_duration`, `onset`, `interval`, `contour`, and `ioi`) provide the best balance between predictive accuracy and information efficiency.

The dominance of pitch information in driving predictive accuracy requires careful interpretation. While the baseline pitch feature alone captures substantial variance, this encompasses not merely raw pitch values but the complex array of pitch-derived relationships that the neural model learns to encode. The model weights implicitly capture interactions between absolute pitch, relative intervals, scale degrees, contour patterns, and their temporal dependencies, relationships that extend far beyond simple note identification. However, this pattern may reflect culture-specific listening strategies rather than universal cognitive principles.

On a large Western melody corpus, SurpriseLSTM’s note-by-note estimates align closely with IDyOM ($\rho_s = 0.639$), validating the recurrent architecture’s ability to learn conditional pitch expectations. The weaker correspondence with AudioIC ($\rho_s = 0.300$) reflects the influence of timbral and polyphonic factors that fall outside our symbolic framework.

Behavioral validation confirms that both SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM capture the inverse relationship between surprise and pleasantness in listener ratings ($\rho = -0.821$ and $\rho = -0.802$ respectively), while AudioIC shows no reliable correlation. The Bach chorale analysis reveals SurpriseLSTM’s superior performance on human behavioral data, achieving stronger correlations with human surprise ratings than IDyOM on both chorales.

This advantage may stem from several factors. SurpriseLSTM’s distributed repre-

sentations may capture more human-like probability distributions and uncertainty patterns compared to IDyOM’s discrete viewpoint combinations. Additionally, the neural model may generalize better to unseen musical styles like Bach chorales, which differ significantly from the training corpus, possibly because distributed representations enable more flexible transfer learning than handcrafted statistical features.

The replication of the Wundt effect demonstrates that SurpriseLSTM reproduces the inverted U-shaped complexity-pleasure relationship, with slightly better explained variance than IDyOM ($R_{\text{adj}}^2 = 0.286$ vs. 0.262). This consistent alignment between model predictions and human aesthetic judgments across multiple paradigms supports theories linking predictive processing to aesthetic experience.

However, both symbolic and neural models leave substantial variance in human behavior unexplained. This limitation points to several areas for future development. Complete models of musical cognition will likely require integration of hierarchical harmonic understanding, long-term structural expectations, and contextual factors such as cultural conditioning and individual differences in musical training.

These results indicate that LSTM-based sequence models, built upon features that capture key aspects of melodic structure, provide a viable approach to modeling musical expectation and surprise. The neural approach’s ability to learn distributed representations may offer advantages over purely statistical methods, particularly for generalization across diverse musical styles. Future work should extend this framework to polyphonic contexts and incorporate timbral information to bridge symbolic and audio-based approaches to musical cognition.

Chapter 6

Neural vs. Statistical Musical Expectation

6.1 Chapter Overview

While the previous chapter demonstrated that both SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM can predict human melodic surprise, fundamental questions remain about their underlying mechanisms and relative strengths. This chapter investigates the deeper architectural and cognitive differences between neural and statistical approaches to modeling musical expectation. We examine how these models perform under different training conditions, their ability to handle diverse musical contexts, and what their similarities and differences reveal about human musical cognition.

Our analysis focuses on three key questions: First, how do training data characteristics affect model performance and what does this reveal about ecological validity? Second, do the models show different response patterns in cadential versus non-cadential musical contexts? Third, what do the convergences and divergences between these architecturally distinct approaches tell us about the computational principles underlying human musical expectation?

6.2 Data and Experimental Design

Our analysis uses the AC/NC stimuli corpus (Dataset 6) from Morgan et al. [38], comprising 45 pairs of melodic stems designed to create contrasting expectation conditions. Each pair consists of an Authentic Cadence (AC) version ending with an implied dominant harmony that strongly suggests tonic resolution, and a Non-Cadence (NC) version designed to avoid strong directional expectations. This controlled design allows us to examine how models respond to contexts with clear versus ambiguous harmonic implications.

We compare three model configurations: SurpriseLSTM trained on the large, diverse Tegrity corpus (Dataset 1), IDyOM trained on the smaller Western dataset (Dataset 2), and IDyOM trained on the same Tegrity corpus as SurpriseLSTM. We trained IDyOM using the `cpintfip` viewpoint together with the linked `cpintfref` \otimes `dur-ratio` combination shown by Pearce [7] to best predict pitch expectancy. This design isolates the effects of training data scale and diversity from architectural differences, enabling us to assess both the scalability and generalization capabilities of each approach.

Human behavioral data comes from the original Morgan et al. [38] study, where 50 musically trained participants performed a melodic cloze task. For each stimulus, we analyze the distribution of sung continuations as empirical probability distributions over scale degrees, allowing direct comparison with model predictions.

6.3 Statistical Analysis

We employ multinomial logistic regression (`mlogit`) to quantify each model’s ability to predict human responses. The analysis uses scale degree (1-7) as the categorical outcome variable, with model-predicted log probabilities as continuous predictors. We fit separate models for combined AC+NC data and NC-only data, allowing us to assess performance both across all contexts and specifically in ambiguous musical situations.

To evaluate model performance comprehensively, we compute several complementary metrics: containment rates measuring the fraction of cases where the human top choice falls within the model’s top-k predictions, Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) assessing the typical ranking position of human preferences in model predictions, and expected log-probability measuring how well model distributions match human response patterns.

We also analyze the average of melody-level error rates, defined as half the sum of absolute differences between human and model probability distributions for each stimulus. This metric provides an intuitive measure of distribution mismatch, where values near 0 indicate perfect alignment and values near 1 indicate completely opposite distributions.

6.4 Results and Analysis

6.4.1 Training Data Dependencies

The mlogit regression results reveal important insights about how the models handle large-scale, diverse training data. Table 8 shows that when IDyOM is trained on the smaller Western dataset while SurpriseLSTM uses the diverse Tegrity corpus, both models remain significant predictors of human behavior (IDyOM: coefficient = 0.429, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$; LSTM: coefficient = 1.022, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$). SurpriseLSTM demonstrates a coefficient more than twice as large as IDyOM, indicating substantially stronger predictive power.

Table 8: IDyOM (Western Data) + LSTM (Tegrity Data): Statistical Results

Predictor	AC + NC				NC			
	Est.	SE	z	p-value	Est.	SE	z	p-value
IDyOM	0.429	0.032	13.29	< 2.2e-16***	0.253	0.040	6.31	2.77e-10***
LSTM	1.022	0.041	25.08	< 2.2e-16***	0.771	0.055	13.89	< 2.2e-16***

Table 9 reveals a different pattern when both models are trained on the identi-

Table 9: IDyOM (Tegridy Data) + LSTM (Tegridy Data): Statistical Results

Predictor	AC + NC				NC			
	Est.	SE	z	p-value	Est.	SE	z	p-value
IDyOM	-0.017	0.052	-0.32	0.749	-0.015	0.067	-0.22	0.822
LSTM	1.249	0.042	30.09	< 2.2e-16***	0.906	0.059	15.42	< 2.2e-16***

cal large-scale Tegridy dataset. Here, IDyOM’s coefficient becomes non-significant (AC+NC: coefficient = -0.017, $p = 0.749$; NC only: coefficient = -0.015, $p = 0.822$), while SurpriseLSTM maintains strong performance (coefficient = 1.249 and coefficient = 0.906 respectively, both $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$).

This pattern does not indicate that IDyOM trained on Tegridy performs poorly in isolation. When evaluated alone, it achieves a significant coefficient of 0.762 ($p < 2 \times 10^{-16}$). Rather, the results suggest that SurpriseLSTM’s predictions subsume the variance explained by IDyOM when both are trained on the same diverse dataset. The neural model’s distributed representations appear to capture all the patterns that IDyOM’s explicit statistical mechanisms detect, plus additional regularities that IDyOM cannot access.

This finding has important implications for understanding the relationship between neural and statistical approaches. When trained on diverse, large-scale data (conditions that better approximate real-world musical exposure) the neural model’s learned representations encompass the predictive capacity of explicit statistical modeling while extending beyond its limitations. IDyOM’s handcrafted viewpoint combinations may represent a subset of the patterns that emerge naturally from SurpriseLSTM’s end-to-end learning process.

The average melody-level error analysis in Table 10 reinforces this interpretation. SurpriseLSTM achieves consistently lower error rates than IDyOM across all conditions (AC: 0.581 vs. 0.686; NC: 0.546 vs. 0.579).

Table 10: Average melody-level error for each model

	Model	AC	NC
Tegridy	LSTM	0.581	0.546
	IDyOM	0.686	0.579
Western	IDyOM	0.627	0.612

6.4.2 Cadential Context Analysis

Figure 5 reveals systematic differences in how models handle cadential versus non-cadential contexts. In AC contexts, human listeners show strong convergence on the tonic (73% of responses on scale degree 1), reflecting the powerful expectation created by implied dominant harmony. SurpriseLSTM captures this tendency with moderate concentration (30%), while IDyOM’s performance varies dramatically by training dataset: the Western-trained version achieves better tonic prediction (29%) than the Tegridy-trained version (19%).

The performance metrics in Table 11 show SurpriseLSTM achieving good accuracy in cadential contexts (Note@Top-1: 57.8%) with the best distribution fit (log-probability: -5.079). Both the Western-trained IDyOM and SurpriseLSTM perform reasonably well when harmonic expectations are clear and strong.

NC contexts present a more challenging test of model capabilities. Human responses become distributed across multiple scale degrees, reflecting genuine uncertainty about continuation. Here, SurpriseLSTM demonstrates superior performance across all metrics in Table 12, achieving 40% accuracy at Note@Top-1 compared to IDyOM’s 15.6% (Western) and 26.7% (Tegridy). The neural model’s distributed representations appear better suited to capturing the uncertainty that characterizes human cognition in ambiguous musical contexts.

Table 11: Model performance for **AC** (cadence) cases. Containment: fraction where the human top choice is in the model’s Top- k (Note = exact pitch, PC = pitch class). Ranking: MRR of the human top choice. Distribution fit: expected log-probability (higher is better).

Category	Metric	LSTM (tegridy)	IDyOM (western)	IDyOM (tegridy)
Containment	Note@Top-1	0.578	0.622	0.267
	PC@Top-1	0.622	0.556	0.178
	Note@Top-3	0.867	0.778	0.689
	PC@Top-3	0.889	0.778	0.733
Ranking	Note MRR	0.740	0.724	0.518
	PC MRR	0.773	0.705	0.478
Distribution fit	Log-prob	-5.079	-5.115	-5.254

Table 12: Model performance for **NC** (non-cadence) cases. Metrics as in Table 11.

Category	Metric	LSTM (tegridy)	IDyOM (western)	IDyOM (tegridy)
Containment	Note@Top-1	0.400	0.156	0.267
	PC@Top-1	0.511	0.244	0.267
	Note@Top-3	0.667	0.622	0.578
	PC@Top-3	0.822	0.622	0.556
Ranking	Note MRR	0.546	0.416	0.466
	PC MRR	0.663	0.485	0.473
Distribution fit	Log-prob	-5.610	-6.076	-5.467

6.4.3 Architectural and Cognitive Implications

Despite architectural differences, SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM show substantial correlation ($\rho_s = 0.639$ from Chapter 5), suggesting architecture-independent properties of melodic expectation. Both models demonstrate sensitivity to statistical regularities in musical sequences, whether captured through explicit n-gram modeling or learned distributed representations.

However, the differential performance across training conditions and musical contexts reveals important mechanistic distinctions. SurpriseLSTM’s robustness to diverse training data and superior handling of ambiguous contexts suggests that distributed neural representations may more faithfully capture the context-sensitive nature of human musical cognition. The neural architecture’s ability to learn hierarchical features and maintain uncertainty distributions that may align better with human cognitive processes than explicit statistical tabulation.

The dominance of tonic responses across both human data and model predictions indicates a bias toward tonal stability that transcends specific architectural implementations. However, this bias appears stronger in human listeners than in either computational model, suggesting that human musical cognition incorporates explicit knowledge about tonal hierarchy beyond what emerges from pure statistical learning.

6.5 Discussion

These findings shows several aspects of computational approaches to musical expectation. The relationship between SurpriseLSTM and IDyOM when trained on large-scale datasets reveals not that IDyOM fails, but rather that neural models may represent a more comprehensive computational framework. When both models are trained on diverse musical data that better approximates real-world listening conditions, SurpriseLSTM’s distributed representations subsume the predictive patterns captured by IDyOM’s explicit statistical mechanisms while extending beyond their scope.

This subsumption suggests that handcrafted viewpoint combinations in statistical models may represent a subset of the patterns that emerge naturally from neural learning processes. Rather than indicating fundamental flaws in statistical approaches, this finding points to the possibility that neural architectures discover and integrate the same statistical regularities that inform explicit models, while simultaneously learning additional relationships that explicit programming cannot easily capture.

The superior performance of SurpriseLSTM in non-cadential contexts supports this interpretation. Human musical expectation in ambiguous contexts likely involves parallel constraint satisfaction where multiple information sources contribute simultaneously to expectation formation. Distributed representations may naturally approximate this uncertainty-aware processing, whereas explicit statistical models require careful engineering to achieve similar flexibility.

The architectural convergence observed between neural and statistical approaches (their substantial correlation despite fundamental differences) suggests both capture important aspects of statistical learning underlying human musical expectation. However, their divergences reveal that computational mechanisms matter significantly for modeling cognitive processes. Neural models' ability to learn hierarchical feature representations and maintain uncertainty may align more closely with human cognitive architecture than statistical systems.

These results also highlight the importance of training data diversity in evaluating cognitive models. Real-world listeners encounter enormous stylistic heterogeneity throughout their lives, and computational models must demonstrate robustness under these conditions to claim ecological validity. The finding that neural approaches better handle diverse training conditions suggests they may provide more realistic approximations of human learning processes.

However, both modeling approaches leave substantial variance unexplained, particularly in complex musical contexts. This limitation indicates that complete models of musical cognition will require integration of hierarchical harmonic understand-

ing, long-term structural dependencies, and cultural conditioning factors that shape individual listening strategies. The current results suggest that while neural approaches may provide a more comprehensive foundation, significant theoretical and computational advances are still needed to fully capture human musical cognition.

Figure 5: Distribution of scale degrees for Human, LSTM, and IDyOM models. Authentic Cadence (left column) and Non-Cadence (right column) are compared, with IDyOM shown in two variants (trained on Tegridy dataset and the Western dataset).

Chapter 7

Discussion and Future Work

7.1 Summary of Contributions

This thesis introduced SurpriseLSTM, a neural network model that applies statistical learning and probabilistic prediction principles to melodic expectation, demonstrating that recurrent architectures can effectively model musical surprise from basic note-level features. Through systematic comparison with established benchmarks across multiple evaluation paradigms, we have provided the first comprehensive assessment of neural versus statistical approaches to modeling musical expectation in the monophonic domain.

Empirically, we demonstrated that SurpriseLSTM matches or exceeds IDyOM’s performance in predicting human surprise judgments across five complementary validation tasks. The model successfully captures the inverse relationship between surprise and pleasantness, reproduces the classical Wundt effect, and provides superior fits to human entropy profiles in Bach chorales.

Theoretically, our findings reveal important distinctions between neural and statistical approaches. When trained on large-scale, diverse datasets that better approximate real-world musical exposure, SurpriseLSTM’s distributed representations subsume the predictive patterns captured by IDyOM’s explicit statistical mechanisms while extending beyond their scope. This suggests that neural architectures may

naturally discover and integrate the same regularities that inform statistical models, while simultaneously learning additional relationships that explicit programming cannot easily capture.

7.2 Implications for Musical Cognition

Our results provide several insights into the computational principles underlying human musical expectation. The dominance of pitch-related features in driving predictive accuracy suggests that melodic contour and interval relationships constitute the primary feature of musical expectation in Western tonal music. However, this finding requires careful interpretation: the neural model's `pitch` representation encompasses complex interactions between absolute pitch, relative intervals, scale degrees, and temporal dependencies that extend far beyond simple note identification.

The superior performance of SurpriseLSTM in ambiguous musical contexts (particularly non-cadential passages where human expectations are distributed rather than focused) suggests that human musical cognition relies on uncertainty-aware processing mechanisms. Distributed neural representations may better approximate the parallel constraint satisfaction processes that characterize human expectation formation, where multiple information sources contribute simultaneously to probabilistic predictions.

The consistent alignment between model predictions and human aesthetic judgments across multiple paradigms supports theories linking predictive processing to musical enjoyment. The replication of the Wundt effect demonstrates that computational models of surprise can capture fundamental relationships between complexity and preference, suggesting that aesthetic experience may emerge from optimal calibration of predictive mechanisms.

However, our findings also highlight significant limitations in current computational approaches. Both neural and statistical models leave substantial variance in human behavior unexplained, particularly in complex musical contexts. This suggests that

complete models of musical cognition will require integration of hierarchical harmonic understanding, long-term structural expectations, and cultural conditioning factors that shape individual listening strategies.

7.3 Extensions to Polyphonic and Audio Domains

The most immediate extension of this work involves incorporating harmonic and polyphonic information. Real-world musical experience typically involves multiple simultaneous voices, harmonic progressions, and textural complexity that may alter expectation formation processes. Preliminary evidence from our cadence analysis suggests that even monophonic melodies invoke implicit harmonic expectations, but explicit modeling of harmonic context remains essential for comprehensive musical cognition models.

7.4 Cross-Cultural and Individual Differences

Our finding that pitch relationships dominate predictive accuracy in Western tonal music raises important questions about cultural universality. Many non-Western musical traditions prioritize rhythmic complexity, timbral variation, or microtonal pitch relationships that may require different modeling approaches. Cross-cultural validation represents a next step for establishing the generalizability of computational models of musical expectation.

7.5 Conclusion

This thesis demonstrates that neural approaches to modeling musical expectation can effectively capture human surprise judgments and aesthetic preferences while revealing important insights about the computational principles underlying musical cognition. The distributed representations learned by neural networks appear to subsume the patterns captured by explicit statistical models while extending beyond their limitations, suggesting that end-to-end learning may provide more comprehensive approximations of human cognitive processes.

However, significant challenges remain in developing complete computational models of musical cognition. The substantial unexplained variance in human behavior, the limitations of monophonic symbolic representations, and the cultural specificity of current approaches all point toward the need for more sophisticated theoretical frameworks and computational methods.

Future progress will likely require integration across multiple levels of analysis: from acoustic feature extraction to cultural conditioning, and across multiple disciplinary perspectives, including cognitive science, musicology, computer science, and cultural studies. The ultimate goal of understanding human musical cognition remains distant, but the computational tools and empirical methods developed in this thesis provide a foundation for continued progress toward this question about human nature and aesthetic experience.

The code and pre-trained models developed for this work are publicly available to facilitate replication and extension by the research community. We encourage future investigations that build upon these foundations while addressing the limitations and opportunities identified throughout this thesis.

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